

SEMI-BLIND CHANNEL ESTIMATION FOR OFDM SYSTEMS VIA AN EM-BLOCK ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a semi-blind channel estimation method based on an Expectation-Maximization Block algorithm (EM-Block). In the OFDM communication context, such an algorithm still have a linear arithmetical complexity. However, it yields to an SNR improvement going up to 3 dB compared to classical training sequences based channel estimation method in the context of 5 GHz OFDM WLANs. The new algorithm performs better than already existing recursive algorithms and use much less prior information on the channel coefficients.

1. INTRODUCTION

In OFDM transmission context, the problem of intersymbol interference is avoided by the insertion of cyclic prefix between consecutive transmitted blocks. At the receiver, this results in the frequency domain, after demodulation by the FFT, to scalar multiplication channel effect. Each subcarrier is attenuated by the corresponding narrowband subchannel coefficient to be estimated.

Classical methods estimate these coefficients relying on known training sequences, assuming that the channel does not vary between two training sequences. In order to cope with Doppler effect due to the mobility of wireless systems, the reference sequences must be repeated more often resulting in a significant loss in the useful bitrate. Alternatively, performance and mobility can be further enhanced by refining the channel coefficients by maximum likelihood estimation (ML) or by maximum “à posteriori” estimation (MAP). The Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm [1] provide iteratively accurate estimates of the ML using the training sequences as initialization of the estimation. EM-based semi-blind channel estimation methods have already been proposed in the OFDM context [2], [3], [4]. In the present paper, we propose an EM-Block algorithm that outperform the already existing ones, in this context arithmetical complexity is linear. The proposed algorithm realizes a trade-off between the channel variation and the number of observations associated with each channel coefficient to be estimated.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the basic notations and recall the OFDM systems. Section 3 presents the proposed EM-Block algorithm. In Section 4, we provide some simulations illustrating the performance of our algorithm and the conclusions of this

study are summarized in Section 5.

2. DEFINITIONS AND NOTATIONS

We consider a conventional OFDM transceiver scheme depicted in figure 1, in which a base band discrete time model of the system is provided. The reader could refer to [5] for continuous time formulation of OFDM systems.

In this model, some side entries of the size P IFFT are zeros and only N of the P subcarriers available are effectively used. The main idea of OFDM transmissions is to turn the channel convolution effect into a multiplicative one [6]. In this goal, the block of data $\underline{x} = [x_1, \dots, x_N]^T$ is modulated in time domain by IFFT processing and some redundancy into the transmitted signal is introduced by cyclic prefix extension so that the overlapping introduced by the channel memory $h = [h_1, \dots, h_L]^T$ corresponds to that of a circular convolution of $\underline{x}$ and h . Consequently, the channel is viewed in the frequency domain after demodulation by the FFT as parallel flat fading channels. Hence, the block $\underline{x}$ can easily be retrieved from the corresponding received block $\underline{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_N]^T$ by FFT and IFFT. With $\underline{h} = [h_1, \dots, h_N]^T$, the OFDM system we consider can be modeled by the following equation:

$$\underline{y} = \text{Diag}(\underline{H})\underline{x} + \underline{n} \quad (1)$$

Where $\underline{H} = SF\underline{h}$, F is the $P \times P$ Fourier matrix, and S is the $N \times P$ matrix selecting the N information sub-carriers $S = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{N, \frac{P-N}{2}} & \mathbf{I}_N & \mathbf{0}_{N, \frac{P-N}{2}} \end{bmatrix}$.

Note that only the L first components of $\underline{h}$ are not null. L corresponds to the cyclic prefix length. OFDM systems are designed such that $L < P$ (in IEEE802.11a $L = P/4$). Each taps are assumed independent and Rayleigh distributed.

3. THE EM-BLOCK CHANNEL ESTIMATOR FOR OFDM SYSTEM

In this section we detail our OFDM semi-blind channel estimation method. First, we recall the EM procedure.

3.1 The EM algorithm principle

The EM algorithm is a two-step iterative procedure maximizing the likelihood function [1] or the probability “à posteriori” [7]. It aims to derive the parameters θ of a system from the observations of its output y (observable) without knowing its input x (hidden variables). The procedure is the following:

Figure 1: Conventional OFDM Transceiver

- Starting from an estimate $\hat{\theta}^{(0)}$ of the parameter θ
- At iteration i , we perform subsequently the:
 - Expectation step (E-step):

$$\text{compute } Q(\hat{\theta}, \hat{\theta}^{(i)}) = \mathbb{E}_x[\log(P(x|y, \hat{\theta}^{(i)}))]$$

- Maximization step (M-step):

$$\hat{\theta}^{(i+1)} = \underset{\theta}{\text{argmax}} Q(\theta, \hat{\theta}^{(i)})$$

There are many practical modified and extended versions of the EM algorithm [7], which have been conceived to deal with many encountered problems such that local maxima, slow convergence, or to maximize others functions of interest like a probability “à posteriori”.

3.2 The EM-Block algorithm

The EM algorithm can be applied to solve our channel estimation problem by considering the block of observations y_m :

$$y_m = H_m x_m + n_m, \quad m = 1, \dots, N$$

Note that the ML estimator requires, to be consistent, many observations y_m for each parameter H_m . With this in mind, and relying on the fact that these channel coefficients H_m are in practice, like in the HIPERLAN/2 [9] wireless LAN context, strongly correlated, we can consider the model (2) below:

$$\underline{y} = X \underline{\tilde{H}} + \underline{n} \quad (2)$$

where $\underline{\tilde{H}} = [H_0, \dots, H_0, \dots, H_{q-1}, \dots, H_{q-1}]^T$ denotes the total channel vector considered now as constant on each

sub-block of size T , such that $N = qT$. The noise vector is denoted by $\underline{n} = [n_0, \dots, n_{N-1}]^T$ and supposed to be white Gaussian with variance $1/K$. We suppose that the hidden variables x_i , are uniformly distributed and take values on a M size constellation $\{s_1, \dots, s_M\}$. Thus, the possible matrix values of $X = \text{Diag}(x_1, \dots, x_N)$ are the $S_{\underline{m}} = \text{Diag}(s_{m_1}, \dots, s_{m_N})$, $\underline{m} = [m_1, \dots, m_N]^T \in \{1, \dots, M\}^N$. Finally, if $\underline{H} = [H_0, \dots, H_{q-1}]^T$ denotes the vector of the channel coefficients to be estimated, then one has: $\underline{\tilde{H}} = B \underline{H}$, where B is the $N \times q$ matrix obtained by the tensorial product $I_q \otimes [1, \dots, 1]^T$. It satisfies the equations below:

$$B^* \text{Diag}(z_0, \dots, z_{N-1}) B = \text{Diag}(z_0 + \dots + z_{T-1}, \dots, z_{(q-1)T} + \dots + z_{N-1}) \quad (3)$$

$$B^* [z_0, \dots, z_{N-1}]^T = [z_0 + \dots + z_{T-1}, \dots, z_{(q-1)T} + \dots + z_{N-1}]^T \quad (4)$$

These important relations will be used to show that the EM-Block algorithm still have low arithmetical complexity (linear) as recursive algorithms [4]. Now, for the model (2), the auxiliary function reads:

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\underline{H}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K, K^{(i)}) &= \sum_{\underline{m}} \log(P(\underline{y}, S_{\underline{m}} | \underline{H}, K)) P(S_{\underline{m}} | \underline{y}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)}) \\ &= -K \cdot \sum_{\underline{m}} | \underline{y} - S_{\underline{m}} B \underline{H} |^2 P(S_{\underline{m}} | \underline{y}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)}) \\ &\quad + N \log(K) + cte \end{aligned}$$

Since $P(\underline{y}, S_{\underline{m}} | \underline{H}, K) = P(S_{\underline{m}}) K^N \exp(-K | \underline{y} - S_{\underline{m}} B \underline{H} |^2)$.

In the following asterix denotes trans-conjugated value. By setting to zero the derivative of $Q(\underline{H}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K, K^{(i)})$ with respect to $\underline{H}^*$, we obtain that

$$\underline{H}^{(i+1)} = C^{-1} \underline{V}$$

where the matrix C and the vector $\underline{V}$ are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} C &= \sum_{\underline{m}} B^* S_{\underline{m}}^* S_{\underline{m}} B P(S_{\underline{m}} | \underline{y}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)}) \\ \underline{V} &= \sum_{\underline{m}} B^* S_{\underline{m}}^* \underline{y} P(S_{\underline{m}} | \underline{y}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)}) \end{aligned}$$

Without simplifications, the sums over the multi-index $\underline{m}$ in the expressions of C and $\underline{V}$ lead to exponential arithmetical complexity. We can notice that $S_{\underline{m}}^* S_{\underline{m}}$ are diagonal matrix. Then, using equation (3), the matrix $B^* S_{\underline{m}}^* S_{\underline{m}} B$, as the matrix C , are diagonal and the j -th component of C is given by:

$$C_j = \sum_{l=jT}^{(j+1)T-1} \sum_{\underline{m}} |s_{m_l}|^2 P(S_{\underline{m}} | \underline{y}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)})$$

The emitted symbols are independant and the noise $\underline{n}$ is white, then $P(S_{\underline{m}} | \underline{y}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)}) = \prod_{k=1}^N P(s_{m_k} | y_k, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)})$,

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
C_j &= \sum_{l=jT}^{(j+1)T-1} \left(\sum_{m_l} |s_{m_l}|^2 P(s_{m_l}|y_l, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)}) \right) \times \\
&\quad \times \prod_{k=1, k \neq l}^N \left(\sum_{m_k} P(s_{m_k}|y_k, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)}) \right) \\
&= \sum_{l=jT}^{(j+1)T-1} \left(\sum_{m_l} |s_{m_l}|^2 P(s_{m_l}|y_l, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)}) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, using equation (4), the j -th component of $\underline{V}$ is given by:

$$V_j = \sum_{l=jT}^{(j+1)T-1} \sum_{m_l} s_{m_l}^* y_l P(s_{m_l}|y_l, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)})$$

Thus, the update formula read, for $j = 1, \dots, N$:

$$\begin{aligned}
H_j^{(i+1)} &= \frac{\sum_{l=jT}^{(j+1)T-1} y_l \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M s_m^* P(s_m) \exp(-K^{(i)} |y_l - H_j^{(i)} s_m|^2)}{\sum_{m=1}^M P(s_m) \exp(-K^{(i)} |y_l - H_j^{(i)} s_m|^2)}}{\sum_{l=jT}^{(j+1)T-1} \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M |s_m|^2 P(s_m) \exp(-K^{(i)} |y_l - H_j^{(i)} s_m|^2)}{\sum_{m=1}^M P(s_m) \exp(-K^{(i)} |y_l - H_j^{(i)} s_m|^2)}} \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

Now, by setting to zero the derivative of $Q(\underline{H}, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K, K^{(i)})$ with respect to K , we have:

$$1/K^{(i+1)} = 1/N \sum_{\underline{m}} |y - S_{\underline{m}} B \underline{H}|^2 P(S_{\underline{m}}|y, \underline{H}^{(i)}, K^{(i)})$$

So, using the same line of arguments, the update formula of the noise variance is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
1/K^{(i+1)} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \sum_{l=jT}^{(j+1)T-1} \sum_{m=1}^M |y_l - H_j^{(i+1)} s_m|^2 \\
&\quad \times \frac{P(s_m) \exp(-K^{(i)} |y_l - H_j^{(i)} s_m|^2)}{\sum_{m'=1}^M P(s_{m'}) \exp(-K^{(i)} |y_l - H_j^{(i)} s_{m'}|^2)} \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

This results in a linear arithmetical complexity proportional to $qTM = NM$ for the computation of the $H_j^{(i+1)}$'s and $K^{(i+1)}$. Thus, the complexity of the EM-Block is still linear.

4. SIMULATIONS

The simulations have been performed in the IEEE802.11a [8] or HIPERLAN/2 [9] wireless LAN context: a $N = 64$ carrier 20 MHz bandwidth broadband wireless system operating in the 5 GHz band using a 16 sample CP. A rate $R = 1/2$, constraint length $l = 7$ Convolutional Code (CC) (171/133) is used before bit interleaving followed by 16-QAM mapping. Monte Carlo simulations are run and averaged over 5000 realizations of a BRANC [10] frequency selective channel in order to obtain BER curves. Each frame processed contains 2 known training symbols, followed by 100 OFDM data symbols. The channel estimation process is made using the EM-Block algorithm described in section 3, with 4 iterations in

which the symbol probability $P(s_m)$ is given by the product of the coded bits probabilities composing the symbol s_m : $P(s_m) = \prod_{l=1}^m P(b_l^m)$. The estimates of the bit probabilities $P(b_l^m)$ are performed in the E-step by two iterations of the turbodemodulation process [11], which is an iterative joint demapping algorithm yielding a better estimation of $P(b_l^m)$ than classical methods like BJCR algorithm [12]. The block size is set $T = 10$. Note that our results are robust to the block size parameter choice. Indeed, similar results are obtained with blocks of size $T = 4$.

Figure 2 and 3 represent respectively the results obtained for a static channel and for a channel mobility of 3 m/s. In both cases, the curves are compared to a system without tracking between training sequences called 'none' and two curves obtained by two EM-based channel estimation recursive algorithms presented in [4] called 'EM-OFDM' and 'EM-OFDM(p)', having linear complexity. The 'EM-OFDM' algorithm suppose perfect knowledge of the channel variances of the channel coefficients H_m , whereas in the 'EM-OFDM(p)' case these variances are supposed to follow a linear decreasing profile.

The EM-Block algorithm thus enhance performances in channel estimation without the need of unrealistic assumption like for 'EM-OFDM'. The figures 2 and 3 show that in both the static and mobile cases, our EM-Block algorithm enables a gain of 3 db compared to the classical ('none') method and of 1,5 db, going up to 2 db, compared to the EM-OFDM(p). Note that the performances of the EM-Block algorithm are as good as those of 'EM-OFDM'. The last one, however, is relying on perfect knowledge of the channel coefficients variances.

Figure 2: Simulation results for a static BRANC channel

Figure 3: Simulation results for a BRAN C channel with a mobility of 3 m/s

5. CONCLUSION

We proposed an EM-Block algorithm, with linear complexity, thus enhance performances in channel estimation without the need of unrealistic assumption like for 'EM-OFDM'. Results are encouraging but it is only a first step. Additional work is to consider a channel variation model, which will be introduced in the algorithm while trying to keep a linear arithmetical complexity.

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